

IMPORTANCE OF PREFERRED LOANS IN FINANCIAL SUPPORT OF FAMILY BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: *The article highlights the importance of preferential loans in financial support for family entrepreneurship, which expresses economic opinions on the importance of loans allocated to family entrepreneurship by commercial banks in our country.*

Key words: *small and medium-sized businesses, private entrepreneurship, family entrepreneurship, financial support, preferential loans.*

Enter. We know from world experience that one of the main drivers of economic development is small and medium-sized business. One of the most reliable small and medium-sized businesses is family business. Therefore, as a result of the socio-economic reforms implemented in our country, special importance has been attached to creating additional conditions for the further development and free operation of various forms of entrepreneurship in our economy, in particular, family entrepreneurship. Because family businesses are economic entities that supply the domestic market with quality goods, increase the country's export potential, and create a large number of new jobs in the country. Solving the problems related to the development of family entrepreneurship is very urgent from the point of view of ensuring the stable development of the country's economy.

It is important for small businesses to increase the base of tax payments to the budget in the formation of the market infrastructure of the economy and the competitive environment, to increase the employment of the population by creating new vacancies, and to fill the market with various consumer goods and services. 'rin holds. Additional measures to improve the financing of business initiatives of the population are being implemented within the family business development programs. In 2024, it is planned to provide a number of benefits to the family business sector. As a proof of our opinion, it was mentioned that "In the case of a decrease in the main rate of the Central Bank, the interest rate on resource funds and loans will be proportionally reduced, and in the case of an increase, it will remain unchanged..."[1]. Family business and private entrepreneurship, as an area that quickly adapts to changes in the economy, is important in filling the domestic market with necessary consumer goods, expanding new and modern types of services.

The current stage of economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is characterized by the development of small business, giving it wide economic freedom.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

According to the opinions of foreign and local scientists who have studied the field of small and medium business, its development and directions:

M.B. In several of his scientific works, Mamut expressed his opinions about small business and family entrepreneurship, that is, according to his opinion, "Banks and non-banks should work together to develop the practice of microcrediting of small business entities. microcredit operations of credit organizations should not be controlled by the Central Bank"[4].

According to the Nobel laureate M. Yunus, "The main attention should be paid to the social effect of lending when lending to small business entities that are starting work now. He said that after

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the expansion of the financial capabilities of business entities, they will cause an increase in the demand for loans at market rates" [5].

As noted by F. Allen and D. Gale, "They recognize the existence of two systems of financing the activity of small and medium-sized business entities - a system based on the activity of banks and a system based on financial markets, and the first system is relatively important" [6] mentioned.

B.B., one of the mature scientists of our country. Berkinov in his monograph entitled "Ways to increase the potential of family entrepreneurship" considers that the development of family entrepreneurship depends on its provision of material and technical resources, as well as the state's conditions for engaging in these types of activities, and the level of creation of the credit system. shows [7].

I.M. Alimardonov said, "Tax benefits play an important role in the state's support for the process of financing business entities. First of all, the state should revise the tax policy"[8].

S.N. Sayfullaev [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15] socio-economic aspects of the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, problems in the field and ways to overcome them, financial support of small business entities Support mechanisms are studied.

Research methodology.

In the course of the research, the forms of financing of family businesses were comparatively and critically analyzed, and special attention was paid to the sources of financing and the real value of the income. The article compares the scientific-theoretical views of economists on the subject, dividing the loans and microloans given by banks to family business entities into separate groups. Family business entities were selected as the object of research.

Analysis and results.

In our country, within the framework of family entrepreneurship development programs, several measures are being implemented to improve the financing of business initiatives of the population. As a proof of this, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Decision No. PQ-149 "The Ministry of Economy and Finance will allocate 2,027 billion soums from the republican budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan to JSC "Khalq Bank" and 790 billion soums to ADB "Mikrokreditbank" and the Recovery and Development Fund for the financing of targeted programs. direct the funds allocated by AT "Khalq Bank" in the amount of 1,837 billion soums and 1,233 billion soums to ADB "Mikrokreditbank" to increase the authorized capital of these banks"[1]. That is, it was determined that the above funds will be allocated for the development of family business.

If we analyze the 2018-2023 indicators of loans allocated under family business development programs in our republic, in 2018 668.4 billion soums of preferential loans were allocated, and in 2023 this indicator will be 9864.3 billion soums, we can see that in 2023 it will be almost 15 times more than in 2018 (Fig. 1).

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Figure 1. Loans allocated under family business development programs (billion soums)[16]

As a result of consistent reforms being carried out in our country, financing of family business is implemented in several directions. That is, it is being financed by the "Every family entrepreneur" program and the support of farmers, peasant farms and homestead land owners, the development of handicrafts, and employment support funds under local governments. The main part of these funds (more than 90 percent) is financed on the basis of the program "Every family is an entrepreneur" (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Sources of family business financing (billion soums) [16]

Regions have an incomparable role in the development of our country's economy. Therefore, the development of family entrepreneurship in the regions is one of the urgent issues of today. Therefore, it is important to finance family business in the region. 13.0 trillion in order to develop family entrepreneurship in the regions of our country in 2023. Soum funds have been directed. The distribution of these funds by regions is presented in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1

Financing of projects within the framework of family business development programs in 2023 (by region, billion soums) [16]

№	Name of regions	Funds allocated in 2023	From this:		
			due to repayment of previously granted loans	At the expense of the Recovery and Development Fund	from the resources of authorized banks
TOTAL:		13 000	6 900	3 381	2 719
1.	Republic of Karakalpakstan	950	457	342	151
2.	Andijan region	1 100	596	275	229
3.	Bukhara region	1 150	570	324	256
4.	Jizzakh region	790	364	135	290

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5.	Kashkadarya region	1 100	533	327	240
6.	Navoi region	780	396	204	180
7.	Namangan region	950	641	159	150
8.	Samarkand region	1 100	668	231	200
9.	Surkhandarya region	1 091	572	278	241
10.	Syrdarya region	600	319	181	100
11.	Tashkent region	1 060	494	356	209
12.	Fergana region	1 100	636	214	249
13.	Khorezm region	941	484	266	191
14.	Tashkent city	290	171	89	30

It should be noted that these factors are characteristic of economic entities in all regions, and are explained by the fact that the development and implementation of innovations require high costs. According to this, the enterprises that work successfully in market conditions and engage in innovative activities achieve higher economic indicators compared to enterprises that do not engage in this activity.

Conclusions and suggestions.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the following levers to provide preferential loans for the development of family entrepreneurship in the regions of our country:

- control and monitor the targeted use of preferential loans;
- allocation of preferential loans for the use of these loans in several areas of farm development (poultry, rabbit breeding, livestock, beekeeping, fisheries and compact greenhouse);
- providing unsecured loans to landowners and tenants of estates with an area of more than 10 hectares;
- Allocating preferential loans for the construction of 10-hectare compact greenhouses and the organization of fishing activities.

Today, the family business sector of small business is the largest labor market in our country, the main factor in the formation of the middle class of owners, a source of income and well-being for millions of people, who are the most responsible for ensuring the stability of our economy based on the planning and strengthening of their business will be interested.

List of used literature:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish dasturlari doirasida aholining biznes tashabbuslarini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirishga doir qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-1492-son Qarori. Toshkent sh., 2024 yil 2 aprel.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda mikromoliya xizmatlarining o‘rni va ulushini oshirish bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-292-son Qarori. Toshkent sh., 2023 yil 4 sentyab.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish dasturlari doirasida aholining biznes tashabbuslarini qo‘llab-quvvatlashni yangi bosqichga olib chiqishga doir qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-39-son Qarori. Toshkent sh., 2023 yil 31 yanvar.
4. Мамут М.В. Микрофинансирование: новые возможности финансово-кредитной системы. // Банковское дело. – Москва, 2009. - № 4. – С. 96 - 99.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

5. Мухаммад Юнус, Алан Жоли. Создавая мир без бедности: социальный бизнес и будущее капитализма. Пер. с англ. – М.: Альпина Паблишерз, 2010. – 307 с.
6. Allen F., Gale D. Comparing Financial Sestems. – Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press, 2000. – P. 42.
7. Berkinov B.B. Oilaviy tadbirkorlik salohiyatini oshirish yo‘llari. Monografiya. – T., 2019 y. 21b.
8. Alimardonov I.M. Kichik biznes sub’ektlarini moliyalashtirishning ayrim dolzarb masalalari. //Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar. 5-son, sentyabr-oktyabr, 2017 yil 3 b.
9. RM Eshdavlatovich, SS Nosirovich, GS Baxodirovich, KS Elamanovich. Improving The Benthofauna In The Fishery As An Indicator Of The Ecological Condition Of The Water Bodies. Int. J. of Aquatic Science, 2021. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:u5NHmVD_uO8C
10. СН Сайфуллаев. ПАНДЕМИЯ ШАРОИТИДА ОИЛАВИЙ ТАДБИРКОРЛИКНИ МОЛИЯВИЙ ҚЎЛЛАБ-ҚУВВАТЛАШНИ СТАТИСТИК ЎРГАНИШ. Архив научных исследований, 2022. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:UeHWp8X0CEIC.
11. SS Nosirovich, Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikga kiritilgan investisiyalarni statistik baholash. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2021. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:d1gkVwhDpl0C
12. Хужакулов Х.Д., Сайфуллаев С.Н. Инновацион иктисодиёт шароитида кичик бизнес ва хусусий тadbirkorlik ривожланишини статистик баҳолаш. “Ўзбекистон статистика ахборотномаси” илмий электрон журнали. 2020,1-сон. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:IjCSPb-0Ge4C
13. Сайфуллаев С.Н. Худудларни инновацион ривожланишида кичик бизнес ва хусусий тadbirkorlik фаолиятини panel тахлили асосида эконометрик моделлаштириш. “Молия” илмий журнали, 2023. 2-сон. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:5nxA0vEk-isC
14. Sayfullayev S.N. Statistical analysis of the status and development of small entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan //SAARJ Journal on Banking & Insurance Research. – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 4. – S. 91-96. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=-6eluLQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=-6eluLQAAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC
15. Сайфуллаев, С. (2023). Статистическая оценка и прогнозирование предпринимательской активности на территориях республики Узбекистан. Международный бюллетень прикладной науки и технологий, 3(5), 237–244. Получено с <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/1369>.
16. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki ma’lumotlari //cbu.uz.
17. Urunov Ravshanbek Sadullaevich. (2022). the digital economy conditions Monte Carlo method in statistical study of sustainable development of regions. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(3), 575–578. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7M8KQ>
18. Urunov Ravshanbek Sadullaevich. (2022). Statistical assessment of the sustainable development of the economy of khorezm region. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(1), 132–136. Retrieved from <https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/980>